

Mitigating stellar activity using line selections for Least-Squares Deconvolution

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Stellar magnetic activity represents a serious obstacle to the search and characterisation of small exoplanets with the radial velocity (RV) technique. It contaminates the data sets with spurious signals, known as “jitter”, that can either mimic or hide the presence of a planetary companion [e.g., 1]. This is a crucial aspect when observing M dwarfs, since they are key targets for future planet atmospheric characterisation missions, like Ariel [2]. M dwarfs have indeed favourable properties such as closer habitable zones (increased detection probabilities with RV or transit method) and higher Earth-like planets occurrence rates [3], but can manifest intense magnetic activity resulting in RV signals of hundreds of m s^{-1} , i.e. two orders of magnitude larger than the signature of an Earth-like planet.

The sensitivity toward small planets depends mainly on our ability to filter out activity-induced RV jitter from the data sets. Knowing from previous studies that spectral lines are affected differently by magnetic activity [4], we studied how to reduce effectively the jitter by selecting different sets of lines to use in Least-Square Deconvolution (LSD, [5]). Here, I provide a summary of the line selections for LSD and their impact on the dispersion of RV data sets presented in [6].

Observations

We used optical spectropolarimetric observations of EV Lac (GJ 873). This is a very active M4.0 dwarf, with a rotation period of 4.38 days, and whose magnetic properties were studied by [7] and [8]. The data set comprises 57 observations collected between 2005 and 2016 with ESPaDOnS and NARVAL, two twin spectropolarimeters located at Canada-France-Hawaii Telescope (CFHT) in Hawaii and Telescope Bernard Lyot (TBL) in France, respectively.

The extraction of unpolarised (Stokes I) and circularly polarised (Stokes V) profiles from the spectra was performed with LSD. This numerical technique assumes the spectrum to be the convolution between a mean line profile and a line list or mask, i.e. a Dirac comb describing the arrangement of spectral lines along with their associated properties such as wavelength, depth, excitation potential, and sensitivity to Zeeman effect. We adopted a synthetic mask with $T_{eff} = 3500 \text{ K}$, $\log g = 5.0 \text{ [cm s}^{-2}\text{]}$, and $v_{micro} = 2 \text{ km s}^{-1}$, and containing 4216 lines in range 350–1080 nm. By deconvolving the observed spectrum with the mask, we combine the information of thousands of spectral lines and retrieve both a Stokes I and V profile with enhanced signal-to-noise ratio (S/N). The Stokes I profile is then modelled with canonical methods similarly to a cross-correlation function, in order to measure radial velocities.

The following sections describe two approaches to

select specific lines from the mask in order to mitigate the activity-induced RV jitter. The default mask will be referred to as “full” mask, whereas the selections as “sub-masks”. The performance of the sub-masks was assessed by the dispersion of the resulting RV data set, as we distinguished “stable” (low dispersion) and “unstable” (high dispersion) selections. Furthermore, we computed the precision of a sub-mask with 100 Monte Carlo injections of white noise in the spectra and obtaining RV data sets for each case. This way we determined whether a sub-mask was photon noise limited.

Figure 1: Radial velocity curves and sine fit residuals phase-folded at stellar rotation period for three data sets obtained with three line lists: full, red lines and blue lines. The dispersion is only reduced by 6%, compared to using the full mask, indicating that a straightforward parametric selection is not suitable to mitigate the RV jitter.

Parametric selection

The RV data set computed with the full mask is characterised by a RV RMS of 167 m s^{-1} and a precision of 8 m s^{-1} , indicating that stellar activity is indeed the dominant source of noise. To mitigate such contamination, we first test a direct line selection approach, consisting in splitting the full mask according to the line properties and physical arguments.

The signal from activity surface features like spots is chromatic [9], hence we isolated red ($\lambda > 550 \text{ nm}$) and blue ($\lambda < 550 \text{ nm}$) lines to locate spectral regions where the dispersion is reduced. As illustrated in Figure 1, the RMS increases up to 4% in both cases, compared to the full mask. We selected shallow ($d < 0.6$), intermediate ($0.6 < d < 0.8$) and deep ($d > 0.8$) lines, which should be decreasingly sensitive to convective velocity fields [10]. In this case, we only see an improvement in RV RMS of 6% with the deep sub-mask. Finally, we used the Lande factor (g_{eff}) to distinguish between magnetically sensitive ($g_{eff} > 1.2$) and insensitive ($g_{eff} < 1.2$) lines, as past studies reported measurable Zeeman broadening for EV Lac [11]. We note a boost in RMS of 20% and a decrease of

10% for the two cases, respectively. We therefore conclude that a line parametric selection does not yield a sub-mask that is substantially more stable than the full mask.

Randomised selection

A second approach consists in building a large number of sub-masks by selecting lines randomly from the full mask, and storing the RMS of the associated RV data set. From the resulting distribution of RV RMS, we can discriminate between stable and unstable sub-masks. In practice, we separate three groups of stable sub-masks depending on whether their RMS is lower than the 10th, 5th, and 1st percentile, and we merge the lists to obtain three sub-masks for each percentile group.

We benchmarked our analysis on the 2010 data set of EV Lac. The dispersion and precision obtained using the full mask are 182 and 4 m s⁻¹, respectively. The three percentile sub-masks lead to a RMS decrease of at least 50%, but the precision increases by a factor of three, as a consequence of the lower number of lines used in LSD. For this reason, we applied the algorithm multiple times and merged the most stable sub-mask among the three percentile-defined ones. Merging the output of three runs allowed us to obtain a sub-mask yielding the same benefit in RMS, while keeping the precision on a 5 m s⁻¹ level.

We studied the portability of the benefit over different data sets and activity levels. We used the 2007 and 2006 data sets of EV Lac, finding a similar 50% RMS improvement in the former case, while a severe degradation (42%) in the latter case, due to the small number of observations (7 in total) over which the sub-masks are investigated. We then searched for stable sub-masks using observations of AD Leo (active) and DS Leo (moderately active). In both cases, we obtained an RMS reduction down to the instrumental stability of ~ 30 m s⁻¹ [12], starting from 110 and 40 m s⁻¹, respectively. In all cases, the photon noise remained significantly smaller than the dispersion, meaning that the mitigation is indeed performed on the activity contamination.

We also tested whether the algorithm can be used in the opposite direction, i.e. to single out lines that are more sensitive to noise sources. Using the 2010 data set of EV Lac, we built sub-masks with an associated increase in RMS by a factor of two and with an enhanced phase-modulation. This could be used, for instance, to better constrain the stellar rotation period.

Finally, we injected synthetic planetary signals of 0.3–0.9 M_{Jup} on a 10 days circular orbit around both EV Lac and DS Leo. No planet is detectable using the full mask on EV Lac, whereas the percentile sub-masks allow the signal to emerge and the injected RV semi-amplitude to be retrieved within error bars (see Figure 2). For DS Leo,

the planetary signal is consistently extracted in all cases, owing to the lower activity level of the star. This demonstrates that the output sub-masks do not suppress the planetary signal, neither in a high nor a low stellar activity scenario.

Figure 2: Results of the planet injection tests. Top: RV data phase-folded at stellar rotation period, Bottom: RV residuals of the activity sine fit phase-folded at planet orbital period. The signal induced by a 0.6 M_{Jup} mass planet on a 10 days orbit around EV Lac is retrieved within uncertainties with the sub-masks generated with our algorithm, contrarily to the full mask.

Conclusions

We studied the impact of different line selections to compute RV data sets with LSD, in order to find lines that mitigate the jitter and could enable more reliable exoplanet detections around active M dwarfs. We reached the following conclusions: 1) a direct selection based on line parameters is not sufficient to reduce the jitter considerably and 2) a randomised selection allows to build sub-masks that reduce the jitter by at least 50% and that are portable over different data sets and activity levels. The method is also applicable to find lines which are more sensitive to activity or when planetary signals are included, without the danger of suppressing their signal.

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